

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PROJECT	
Project number:	101109983
Project acronym:	CRYOCHICK
Project name:	Innovative Cryopreservation Methods for Chicken Germplasm

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Date:	15/10/2023
Version:	2

1. Data Summary

- CRYOCHICK will not reuse existing data, because the research topic is new and as such reusable data does not (yet) exist for this research project.
- The formats generated by the project will be numerical (.xlsx), graphic (.xlsx) textual (.docx, pdf), film (.avi). Where possible, data will also be stored in open file formats (e.g. .csv in addition to .xlsx).
- The data generated during this Project can be useful for external or internal researchers working on the same topic as the project, as well as serve as a basis for new projects. Additionally, The generated data can be useful to those researchers or students willing to understand the results of our research, its context and conditions of use, and to re-run the reported analyses. This may help to provide continuity to the research or to use it to build new projects
- The data generated will have a maximum of 10 Gb
- The data will be obtained from the characterization of chicken sperm, chicken gonadal germ cells as well as from the analysis done to the current strategy of CGN.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Data will be stored in Zenodo which assigns a DOI to every published set of data.
- Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments.
- The metadata will include author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata should include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication. The metadata will include keywords to optimize the possibility for discovery and potential re-use.
- Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing.
- Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

The data will be deposited in the open repository Zenodo. When data is published in Zenodo, a unique, persistent identifier [Digital Object Identifier (DOI)] is assigned to it.

Data:

Most of the data will be made openly available with CC BY licence; however we will be performing online surveys by sending surveys to the farmer's, other gene banks' or stakeholders' email address. The data related to any personal or other sensitive data from these surveys will not be openly available and will at most be shared under formal agreements for which the Information Security Officer and the Privacy officer are consulted. These personal/sensitive data will be removed when not required for verification of research.

Metadata:

- The metadata will be under CC BY licence. The data, when not containing personal information, will be published in Zenodo where the data will be described with the metadata standard utilized by Zenodo. As such, the metadata does not have to be published separately from the data.
- Data and the applied metadata will remain available for the lifetime of Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.
- Metadata are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which are separate to the data itself.
- All software (version, company, proper reference) necessary to access or read the data will be documented in the readme file, especially in the case when the data cannot also be stored in open file formats. This research project will not generate software.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- The numeric data will use units from decimal metric system and international convention. The formats used for data will be those openly available (.docx, .pdf, .xlsx, .avi) and also stored in open formats (e.g. .pdf, .txt, .csv) where possible.
- Regarding metadata, Zenodo uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML.
- The data will not include reference to other data as we are not reusing data.

2.4. Increase data re-use

The data will be stored in an open repository (Zenodo), that way; they can be re-used in the future.

An open licence CC BY will be applied to the data to facilitate reuse
To make data findable and reproducible, they will be accompanied by:

- The WUR codebook template (see template at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7701727>)
- The WUR readme file template (see template at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7701727>).

Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

The data quality assurance processes will include:

- Supervisors or peers will review the data and results for any anomalies (e.g. unexpected inconsistencies, outliers, correct labeling of data and / or treatments, correct and consistent coding applied, etc.).
- We will consult statisticians.
- We will use repeated measurements to validate results.
- We will use standard and validated protocols where appropriate.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the generation of new data, CRYOCHICK will generate new articles and abstract to congresses. This information will be stored on the W-drive, a storage media managed by WUR (datacenters at WUR) and in Zenodo.

4. Allocation of resources

Dr, Berenice Bernal Juárez will be responsible of the Data Management of CRYOCHICK.

Dr. Bernal will spend at least 10% of its time on research data management to approach the FAIR principles as much as possible.

All costs for 10 year data storage and access management to that data after journal publication or report are covered by the research group / project. The Supervisor of CRYOCHICK and the Project Leader of CGN will decide which data will remain stored and for how long.

5. Data security

Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least. Moreover, the WUR data policy requires data underlying publications to be preserved for at least 10 years. The data will be stored in the W-drive , which is managed network drive of WUR (datacenters at WUR) in which data is automatically backed-up and has secure access management (only accesible to specific added WUR credentials). Data transfer of sensitive data should be requested to the Project Leader of CGN or Supervisor of CRYOCHICK.

6. Ethics

- Personal and other sensitive data will not be made openly available and will at most be shared under formal agreements for which the Information Security Officer and Privacy officer are consulted.
- Personal or other sensitive data will be removed when not required for verification of research. Access management to the data is either managed or approved by the Project leader / Supervisor of the project.
- Informed consents are present when information from humans are involved.
- WUR will use semen kindly provided by the Dutch Research Facility of Cobb Europe. Semen collection will be performed according to the European Council Directive 98/58/EC on protection of animals kept for farming purposes and the European Union Directive 2010/63/UE on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes, following the 3Rs principles. Regarding the authorization for animal experimentation of the rest of institutes, NBGK counts on permission for animal experimentation, including embryo management according to the identification sign: PEI/001/809-2/2015. The Roslin Institute maintains transgenic chicken under licence from the Home Office of the UK government and regulation by the Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986. The experimental work will be carried out at non-protected stages of chicken embryonic development (pre-day 14, i.e. before the 14th day of incubation). These stages are not regulated under the EU law. However training in Schedule 1 euthanizing (legal ways to euthanize a chicken) of pre-day 14 chicke embryos will be carried out by the Institute NACWO (Named Animal Care and Welfare Officer) under regulation of the Roslin Institute AWERB committee.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE